

A Critical Study on Digital Marketing with Reference to Different Components of Digital Marketing

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ABSTRACT

Digital Marketing is a part of marketing which uses digital channels. Some examples of Digital channels includes advertise on website, YouTube, Face book and sponsorship on YouTube. Content marketing, Social Media marketing, E-mail Marketing, Search Engine optimization (SEO), Search Engine marketing (SEM) and Web Analytics are components of digital marketing. According to a survey by Internet and Mobile Association of India (IAMAI), India will have around 500 million internet users by June 2018. So result of this digital marketing shows growth in Digital Marketing in India.

KEYWORD: Digital Marketing, E-mail, Search Engine optimization, Search Engine marketing

INTRODUCTION

Digital Marketing is a part of marketing which uses digital channels. Some examples of Digital channels includes advertise on website, YouTube, Face book and sponsorship on YouTube. Whenever you use digital channel for marketing then it is known as digital marketing. Now days, rates of internet service providers go on decreasing their service rates rapidly, the number of users go on increasing. So definitely the population for digital marketing is more than conventional marketing. Advantage of digital marketing over conventional marketing is that you are easily able to trace number of customers watching your advertisement. You are also able to positive and negative result of digital marketing through analysis of data. So there is lot of scope for experiment. ^[1]

Components of Digital Marketing

Following are the components of digital marketing

1. Content marketing
2. Social Media marketing
3. E-mail Marketing
4. Search Engine optimization(SEO)
5. Search Engine marketing(SEM)
6. Web Analytics

1. Content Marketing:

The key to growing a business online is Content marketing. It is concerned with traffic of users, lead and sale. It rotates around creation, publications and promotions of products ^[2]. The Content Marketing Institute, an online resource for information defines content marketing as “Content marketing is a strategic marketing approach focused on creating and distributing valuable, relevant, and consistent content to attract and retain a clearly defined audience — and, ultimately, to drive profitable customer action”^[3].

Content marketing first create awareness between customers. Then customer will automatically do research. The research is to purchase high quality product at low price. Customers start comparing same product on different content marketing site or social media by different vendors. Choose the best vendor. ^[4]

2. Social media marketing:

Now a day’s social media is part and parcel of everyone’s life. Now social media is also play role of effective business platform. While selecting social

media marketing, selecting proper platform is most important. Along with time, efforts and fun is also important. E. g if you are interested in cooking, fitness and fashion then Instagram and what's up plays important role. To use social media as digital marketing there is need to decide theme and study of competitors work style. From this decide content police. It is not short term job. Its ongoing process, which needs research, continues efforts.^[6]

3. E-mail Marketing

Email marketing is said to be one of the strongest digital marketing media. Steps involved in this type of marketing are create email list. Manage email follow up. Compile analytics and use them. Justin Bryant in his video Email Marketing Tips and Tricks for Beginners 2016 discusses some tips for digital marketing using email, these are as follows.

Use the right email service. Make it easy to subscribe. Define your audience. Always have a welcome Email. Encourage subscriber to follow you on social media. Make sure that people will be able to easily unsubscribe. Use short punchy subject lines. Segment your list.^[7]

4. Search Engine optimization(SEO)

A search engine is a software system that is designed to search for information on the World Wide Web. Google, Bing, Yahoo and AOL are major search engines used by number of customers. A customer enters phrases into a search engine to search and receives a list of Web content which includes websites, images, videos or other online data. Search Engine Optimization is marketing your site on the Internet's most popular Search Engines. The primary goal of SEO is to improve traffic to your website from searches on the internet for phrases that are related to your target. A good site has content that is carefully created, with relevant content, well-structured and easily read and indexed by search engines.^[8]

5. Search Engine marketing (SEM)

Search engine marketing (SEM) services help businesses acquire targeted website traffic, build relationships and drive conversions.^[9] It is the practice of marketing through paid advertisements that appear on relevant search engine results pages and websites. These advertisements can have different formats and are paid for through a bidding process. You can even choose which search engines to use and where/when you want your ads displayed so that you

can best reach your audience using your style of advertising.^[10]

6. Web Analytics

Web analytics is the measurement and analysis of data to inform an understanding of customer's behavior across web pages. It measures browsing activities of customers. E. g how many customers visit particular site, how long they stay, how many pages they visit, which pages they visit repetitively. Businesses use it to measure and site performance and purchase conversion rate.^[11]

Future of digital marketing

According to a survey by Internet and Mobile Association of India (IAMAI), India will have around 500 million internet users by June 2018. This will create a fascinating business opportunity to sell services and products to a growing population of tech-savvy internet users.^[12] Because of this, digital marketing can be used to target a large number of customers. It is very cost effective. It provides instant data analytics of your marketing. There is scope of change as per result of data analytics. With these advantages there is very bright future for digital marketing in India.

Conclusion:

As population of internet users goes on increasing, the users who use social media, YouTube, email, online shopping etc. are huge. Because of this digital marketing is growing industry in India. The facilities like data analytics provide instant result of advertising on digital media. It will help to improve the performance of marketing.

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